

Becoming Asian American: Personal Reflections and Messages for My Planetary Science Community

Parvathy Prem

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Caveats

- I do not know Asian American history as well as I know lunar volatiles.
- My thoughts are rooted in my own specific experiences, and are not representative of views held by others who share some of my identities.

The Making of Asian America*

*Also the title of a highly recommended book by Erika Lee.

Center Mural, Asian & Pacific Islander Student Center, Cal Poly Pomona

Asian Americans Count

- ~10% of the US planetary science community identifies as Asian or Asian American (compared to ~7% of the population).

- ~17% of Asians in the US identify as multiracial or Hispanic.
- A significant number of transracial adoptees are Asian (US Census Bureau, 2014).

The Model Minority Stereotype

“...the portrayal of Asian Americans as a successful minority seemed to serve a need; the image quickly caught on and dominated the stage for years.” [Ki-Taek Chun, 1980]

- The model minority stereotype is **(a) false**, and **(b) dangerous**.

Household poverty rates among Asian groups in the US (Pew Research Center, 2019).

- Asian Americans vary widely in terms of educational levels, income, class, immigration status, and English language proficiency.
- The ‘model minority myth’ is often used to discredit other minority groups, leads to backlash against Asians from multiple quarters, and adversely impacts Asian American students.

On Foreignness

“The perpetual foreigner syndrome... shows us that some lines that are supposedly based on citizenship actually cover up lines that are based on race. Because the former is permissible and the latter is not, it becomes easy to rationalize distinctions among people as involving citizenship rather than race.” [Frank H. Wu, 2002]

- ~57% of Asians in the US were born in other countries (Pew Research Center, 2019), a statistic that contains a diversity of personal histories.

“You work hard, you have good output, you build a reputation... But in the end, you’re treated like a spy. That just breaks your heart. It breaks your confidence.”

– Dr. Gang Chen, MIT

On Solidarity and Belonging

“Asian American’ – rather than describing our personally felt identities or describing our family histories – expresses an idea. And that idea is that as Asian Americans, we have to work together to fight for social justice and equality, not only for ourselves, but for all of the people around us.” – Dr. Daryl Maeda

- Become aware of who Asian Americans are, and at least the broad contours of the history of Asians in America.
- Support broad *and* focused *and* intersectional affinity groups.
- Recognize that we work in a field in which nationalism and militarism can manifest in ways that directly impact those we work with.
- Recognize that inclusion is not a zero-sum game. When planning individual or institutional action, think carefully about who is excluded or supported, and why.

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